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Lachrymation, Protest and Identity in Selected Niger Delta Poetry.

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Abstract

This study examines lachrymation and protest as indices of the identity of poetry emanating from the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Four collections of poems, one each by four Niger Delta poets – Tanure Ojaide, Nnimmo Bassey, Ebi Yeibo and Sophia Obi – have been selected for analysis. The study draws insights from the theoretical perspectives of post-colonial ecocriticism as a critical tool for the interpretation of selected poems. It reveals that the poets project their physical landscape as the fulcrum of all other landscapes – social, political and cultural. It further notes that their poetry exhibits a near-obsessive and abiding concern for the physical environment in order to preserve its beauty and ensure harmony between the physical environment and other components of the environment. The study also examines significant aspects of style and techniques such as recurrent images and symbols of seascapes and relevant elements of African oral tradition deployed by the poets to foreground protest and concern for the environment. The study concludes on the note that despite the diversity of the region characterized by cultural plurality, there is a point of convergence in their art as seen in the sustained campaigns of the poets for the preservation of the environment to ensure environmental justice and the ultimate survival of the region.

Keywords: Poetry, Lachrymation, Protest, Identity, Niger Delta.

Introduction

The Niger Delta region in Nigeria is associated with rich natural endowments such as crude oil and rich flora and fauna. However, the region, according to Nwahunanya, has become ‘the albatross of Nigeria’ (xiii), because of the ironic contradictions inherent in the degradation and impoverishment of the region that holds the largest stake in Nigeria’s economic growth. The region was for long seen as the most volatile region in Nigeria because of the violence that often attended the people’s agitation for better treatment by both successive Nigerian governments and multinational companies prospecting and exploiting oil resources in the region. Government deliberate neglect

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and the activities of profit driven multinational oil companies have left the physical landscape of the region devastated and its people largely impoverished. Situated ‘on the Atlantic coast of Nigeria where the Niger River divides into numerous tributaries’ (ANEJ, 2), the Niger Delta boasts remarkable endowment of natural lush vegetation and rich crude oil deposits. The abundant endowment of oil resources accounts for Nigeria’s reputable designation among the leading oil producing countries of the world. This designation ordinarily should confer on the region the enviable status of the most industrialized and most developed region in Nigeria and should equally translate to a life of affluence and comfort for the indigenes. Ironically, the reality of the region is succinctly articulated by Ibiwari Ikiriko who says that, ‘the oil boom in Nigeria has meant doom for the Niger Delta (*Oily Tears*, 7). This unfortunate situation expectedly led to the emergence of irate youths who engaged their perceived exploiters through protests some of which inadvertently turned violent. Such protesters are generally seen by government as militants who sabotage government projects in the region.

Government’s determined efforts to protect its commercial interests in the region at all cost often result in bloody clashes between government forces and indigenes of the region. Literary writers from this region, especially poets have continued to capture the beauty and plight of this region in their works. A careful survey of their works reveals that Niger Delta poetry is dominated by themes of environmental degradation, human deprivation, and economic exploitation; and it is identified with the strong character of protest (Dickson, 56). Thus, the Niger Delta crisis appears to have generated more literature than any other phenomenon in the history of Nigeria as a nation. Ezechi Onyerionwu and Alwell Onukaogu observe that, some Nigerian critics consider the Niger Delta crisis as the biggest event available to Nigerian literature as a subject matter’ (127).

The Nigerian Civil War held the record as the event that attracted the largest literary attention in Nigeria for so long. However, as observed by Nwahunanya, the Niger Delta crisis has overtaken the civil war as the focus of literature in Nigeria. This situation is inevitable because the Niger Delta experience has lasted longer and the impact has been more devastating in a permanent way (Nwahunanya, xiii)

The sustained attention given to the Niger Delta crisis by literary writers has culminated in the emergence of a kind of poetry identified with and characterized by protest; and poetry appears to be the dominant genre of expression of protest by writers from the region. The poetry of Tanure Ojaide, Odia Ofeimun, Ken Saro Wiwa, Ibiwari

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Ikiriko, Nnimmo Bassey, Joe Ushie, Barine Ngaage, Hope Eghagha, Ebi Yeibo among others vibrate with vehement protest against the continued devastation of the Niger Delta. Although the protest also manifest in drama and prose as evident in the works of Tess Onwueme, Ben Okri, Onookome Okome, Isidore Okpewho and others, poetry has been more prolific in this regard. Consequently, this study is conceived to examine lament and protest as identifying characters of Niger Delta poetry. Thus, Tanure Ojaide's *Delta Blues and Home Songs*, Nnimmo Bassey's *We thought it Was Oil but it Was Blood*, Ebi Yeibo's *The Forbidden Tongue* and Sophia Obi's *Tears in a Basket* are studied here as representative of such protest poetry.

Tanure Ojaide belongs to the third generation of Nigerian poets who began to write in the 1980s. Born in the oil rich Delta State of Nigeria, he witnessed in his youth the economic boom propelled by the oil resources exploited in his state as well as the doom it has gradually become for his people. His poetry often traces this transition from boom to doom as can be seen in the poem '**When Green was the Lingua Franca**'. Here the poet employs the trope of reminiscence to recall the pristine Niger Delta of his childhood which 'was teeming with life' (14) and united by the greenness of the landscape. The poet employs concrete images to describe and to foreground the beauty and unity of the Niger Delta environment when it was 'one unbroken park/ teeming with life' (14). Greenness was the common language denominator of the Delta despite the different dialects of the different states in the region.

The poet observes that 'in the forest green was/the lingua franca/ with many dialects' (14). The greenness of the flora was complemented by the diversity of the fauna and aquatic life of the environment, which for the persona, was irresistible as seen in the lines 'snails and koto lured me/ to tear through tangles/ that seasoned my soles/ to defy every distance' (14). These adventures and the obstacles encountered by the persona foreshadow the turbulent future awaiting the poet and his compatriots in their bid to salvage the Delta from those who plunder it. Meanwhile, despite the diversity, there was natural harmony among the inhabitants of the Delta as reported by the persona: 'undergrowth kept as much / alive as overgrowth, the Delta / alliance of big and small'. It was an environment of mutual coexistence and self-sustenance that had a ready 'market of needs, and arena/ of compensation for all' (15). But suddenly, all of this was truncated by the intrusion of another kind of alliance described in stanza five of the poem as coming with 'quakes and a hell of flares' (15). This strange alliance 'broke the bond' of the existing 'Delta alliance' alluded to earlier in the poem. It was an alliance

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with multinational oil companies represented by Shell. This alliance heralded the disconnect between the people and their environment which initially was teeming with life. But now the same environment is inhabited by 'victims of arson' -both man and animal- who are driven paranoid by the constant blasting of explosives to prospect for oil and the subsequent gas flaring which has turned the region into some kind of incinerator. The result is that the order of seasons is altered, thereby driving the 'seasons mental/ and to walk on their heads' (15) while the once lush green forests have become 'a treeful carnage' (15). The waters have suffered an even worse fate as seen in 'the Ethiopia waterfront/ wiped out by prospectors/and streams mortally wounded' (15). The poet regrets that his childhood Delta which teemed with life now breeds death.

The sense of loss continues in the poem '**Season**' in which the poet deploys a plenitude of riverine lexemes to paint a poignant picture of loss. The poem begins thus:

Our towns rose from riverbank of barter
Once the waters sustained coloring from oil slick
If you took fins from fish, would it still be fish? (15).

The words 'riverbank', 'waters', 'oil slick', 'fins' and 'fish' are concrete riverine images meant to convey to the reader the environmental, economic, political and psychological issues involved in the Niger Delta question. For instance, the poet's towns which originally rose from riverbanks have now become a subject of economic bartering, thereby drawing attention to the economic importance of the region. But the barter has resulted in the 'coloring' of the people's waters by slick oil. And the psychological trauma and the economic deprivation resulting from there are captured in the rhetorical device laden with the image of exploitation: 'if you took fins from fish, would it still be fish?' The pristine beauty of the Niger Delta environment as well as its ecological harmony before the advent of oil exploration is accentuated by the use of these familiar images.

The imagery continues in the poem '**Delta Blues**' where the poet re-echoes the idea of the Delta as a lost paradise. The region is here portrayed as a paradise which has been wounded irreversibly and still reeling in pain:

This share of paradise, the delta of my birth,
Reels from an Immeasurable wound

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Barrels of alchemical draughts flow
From this hurt to the unquestioning world
That lights up its life in a blind trust

The image of paradise in the above recalls the original lush green forests of the Delta with its numerous waters. But all this, regrettably has been lost to barrels of alchemical flows which have denuded the forests of their greenery while leaving a wound that bleeds perpetually on the psyche of the people. While not undermining the development which oil exploitation attracts, the poet decries the destruction wrought on 'our shared paradise', thereby breaking the bond between man and the ecosystem and in the process, breaking 'the peace of centuries/ and tainting not only a thousand rivers,/ but also scorching/ the air and soil' (22). The situation is so bad that the entire biosphere is mortally wounded, so that 'the rivers are dark-veined' and have become 'a course of perennial draughts' (22). These were rivers that hitherto served as the lifeblood of the region. Red blood is supposed to course through veins to signify life; but here, the lifeless water that flows through the rivers is dark like black blood which is a symbol of death of the rivers and all life dependent on them. By deploying death-dealing metaphors such as 'scorched air, burning bush, immortal pain, singed, debauched' which show the region as a massive wasteland, the poet negates the image of the beautiful paradise which the Delta symbolized at the outset.

Nnimmo Bassey hails from Akwa Ibom State which is the second largest source of Nigeria's crude oil. Looking at his poetry collection, *We Thought it was Oil but it was Blood*, the title paints a lachrymal picture of the Niger Delta. Like Ojaide's 'When Green was the Lingua Franca', where the poet begins from his childhood days of beautiful memories, Bassey reminisces on the resplendent joy the discovery of oil brought to the people. 'The other day / We danced in the street/ Joy in our hearts/ We thought we were free' (13). But they quickly disappeared like a mirage, as reality dawns on them when in a swift turn 'three young folks fell to our right/ countless more fell to our left/ looking up,/ far from the crowd/ we beheld/ red-hot guns' (13). These lines are reminiscent of the dark days of the military reign of terror on the Niger Delta occasioned by the people's attempts to resist the usurping of their oil wealth. The full intent of the government was not clear to the people initially hence their resistance. But the following lines convey the steel determination of the government: 'Heart jumping / into our mouths/ floating on/Emotion's dry wells/ We leapt in fury/ knowing it wasn't funny/

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Then we beheld/ Bright red pools’ (13). ‘The bright red pools’ captures the mindless waste of life resulting from confrontation with government forces. To show the scope of this destruction, the poet gives the antecedent to the carnage and its possible trajectory in the following lines: ‘First it was the Ogonis/ Today it is the Ijaws/ Who will be slain the next day?’ (13). The result is paralyzing as the following lines show: ‘We see open mouths/ But hear no screams/ Tears don’t flow/ When you are scared/We stand in pools/ Up to our knees’ (14). Despite the shocking massacre visited on the people, the exploitation continues ‘Behind military shields/evil, horrible gallows called oilrigs/drilling our souls’ (14). However, the next lines reveal the collective resolute determination of the poet and his people to continue with the fight, their fate notwithstanding:

 Their pipes may burst
 But our dreams won’t burst

 They may kill all
 But the blood will speak
 They may gain all
 But the soil will RISE (15).

The foregrounding of the word ‘RISE’ in the last line signifies the undying optimism of the people in their quest for liberation. In another poem, ‘**When the Earth Bleeds**’ the poet presents a paradox which encapsulates the stark reality of environmental degradation in the Niger Delta. According to the poet, ‘the oil only flows/ when the earth bleeds’ (17). This fact is contrary to the peddled capitalist view that ‘oil makes things move’. The truth for the poet is that ‘oil makes life stop’, because it is only the metaphoric bleeding of the earth resulting from ‘a thousand explosions in the belly of the earth’ (16) which ultimately debilitates the earth that produces oil. So, whereas oil lubricates the business of the multinationals and lines their pockets, it puts the earth on a ‘sick bed’ made by ‘bleeding rigs’, ‘bursting pipes’ and ‘gas flares’ - all of which spell death for the Niger Delta ecosystem.

The poet therefore, enjoins his people to rise up and defend their environment in the following lines:

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What must we do?
Do we just sit
Wail and mope?
Arise people, Arise
Let's unite
With our fists
Let's bandage the earth. (17)

The poet's concern is not just for man but for the entire ecosystem which has witnessed serious ecocide as a result of such major players as 'Shell, Exxon-Mobil, Texaco, NNPC, Chevron, Agip...' whose greedy and profiteering activities have left 'a mountain of butterflies dead', while they keep ferrying abroad 'their booty of dollars, greed and crude' which ultimately encourages graft and corruption locally by 'making bellies burst as pipes burst' (25). In essence, the poet sees the greedy local beneficiaries of the environmentally detrimental activities of the oil merchants as those whose bellies are bursting with ill-gotten wealth. In the poem '**Gas Flares**', Bassey projects the Niger Delta landscape as one that has been subjected to arson through the different kinds of flares in the region. The poet scoffs at government's continued use of gas flaring, a practice which has been discontinued in other oil producing countries. The adverse effect of gas flaring is evident in the following lines:

The earth gassed
Dynamites rocked the storehouse
Of life
Now the sky is ablaze
Where will the people go? (48)

In the above lines the poet captures the helplessness of the people who are confronted by homelessness having lost their storehouse of life, the sky ...to the flares which he describes as 'belching dragons' that 'attack' with 'leaping tongues of fire' that 'lick' 'roofs' and 'farms' (48). The poet's bitter lament is wrapped in the heart-rending question 'where will the people go?' He attempts to provide an answer by telling them: 'flee the flames/ dive into the creek/fly/ the last tortoise is gone/escape the raging flames' (48). The poet reasons that the creeks and the rivers provide a natural sanctuary

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for the inhabitants in times of grave danger. But he suddenly realizes that even these havens are no longer safe, because even ‘...the sea is ablaze’ and ‘the earth is ablaze’ (48). With this, the poet portrays the environment as unsafe for all of its inhabitants both human and nonhuman. However, the poet again calls for resistance in order to halt the trend.

Ebi Yeibo is another poet from Delta State whose poetry is devoted to the cause of the Niger Delta. His collection, *The Forbidden Tongue* represents the poet’s artistic response to human exploitation in the Niger Delta region. The poet’s protest stems from his conviction that destruction of the physical or natural environment is tantamount to human exploitation.

The Forbidden Tongue is, therefore, a collection of protest poems by which the poet opposes and challenges the continued exploitation of the Niger Delta inhabitants. Through the deployment of poetic devices such as imagery, metaphor, repetition and contrast, the poet projects a tragic vision for the Niger Delta. In the opening poem, ‘**Song**’ for example, the poet persona is cast in the image of a drunkard or a mad man whose song (Poetry) serves as a “scathing manure” to moisten “calcified farmlands”, to “cleanse cringing creeks cadavers and maelstroms/ with searing songs” (19). The alliteration inherent in the preponderance of the voiceless velar plosive /k/ in “cleanse, cringing creeks/cadavers...” and the voiceless sibilant /s/ in “searing songs”, foregrounds the harsh and inhuman exploitation of the people. By employing these alliterative devices, the poet creates a gritty rhythm suggestive of his anger over the exploitation of the people. The harshness of the grating sounds evokes the suffering and pain of the people. More alliterations and repetitions are evident in the poem “Sacrifice” where the persona exposes the greed and avarice of these local traitors whom he calls “renegades”

Who barter a basket of yams
for a healthy bowl of beetles (20).

These are top government officials and traditional rulers who connive with foreigners to exploit their people. The irony and sarcasm embedded in those lines reveal the foolishness of the betrayers who exchange the life sustaining resources of the Delta and the people – the metaphorical “basket of yams” for fleeting riches symbolized here by the paradoxical “healthy bowl of beetles”. These betrayers are so insensitive that they are oblivious of the huge sacrifice made by the people. Instead, together, with their foreign collaborators, they “swoop” on them “like hawks on chicks”. But unknown to

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these saboteurs, they too are objects of exploitation portrayed as lackeys:

Dutiful, like dogs lapping up faeces
Nibbling at Cancerous nipples
Of a listless sweetheart (20).

The poet persona's resolve to champion the protest against human exploitation reverberates in the repetition of "I lie waiting at the crossroads". In addition to creating a significant musical effect which reveals the extent of the exploitation that has left the people lying prostrate and helpless, the technique of repetition emphasizes the severity of the people's situation, especially following the extinguishing of the flicker of hope symbolized by "the rainbow", "the new moon", by the exploiters

Who rape the rainbow
Like a common whore
And murder the new moon
Right on our lap (21).

The resignation of the people is echoed in the poet's lament:

O the somber sacrifice we made
Through murkiest nights
Has turned a painful repository
Of Pig's pee
Desecrating our new dawn;
The shafts of sunray
We saw stripping the persistence of gloom
Now turn a mere dream (21).

It is the dashing of the people's hope and the turning of their collective dream into a mirage that drive the poet's passion for protest as seen in the poem '**Rage of a River**'. Here the poet employs the technique of extended metaphor to justify their protest against human exploitation. The Niger Delta is portrayed as the metaphorical mother hen subjected to constant harassment by the hawk, which "swoops on her chicks" (28). The poet, therefore, sees this as a convincing reason for his artistic protest; and through the use of rhetorical devices, the poet wonders whether any reasonable

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person thinks otherwise:

Who wouldn't whose paradise
Becomes a prostitute's rag
Whose brooks brim
With bilious black blood
Whose dreams host rabid jiggers?
Whose savory savory swamps
Are cauldrons of chemicals
Whose hallowed virginity
Is stolen the wrong way (28)

The implied message in the above lines is adumbrated through the technique of alliteration anchored on rhetorical questions which remind the people of their loss and the need for action. The people have been reduced to wearing "sackcloth" as they behold their paradisiac Delta now "waxed wild on the wings of wreckage" (28) while protesting the despoliation of their land and the slaughter of their youths symbolized by fledgling white eagles.

Sophia Obi is another poet from the Niger Delta whose poetry pulsates with vibrant protest against the official exploitation of the Niger Delta people and its environment. This is quite obvious in the collection *Tears in a Basket*, which contains poems that address issues which Joe Ushie describes as 'the raw realities that confront the creative writer from the Niger Delta'. In the poem '**Tomorrow's Debris**', the poet laments the incessant slaughter of youths by government forces who are bent on subduing them so that government can have its way to plunder the wealth of the Delta. The poet is pained that these youths whose lives are extinguished prematurely only try to protect and defend what rightfully belongs to them. The people are portrayed as impoverished through the continued exploitation of their resources. The poverty of the people finds expression even in their dwellings of 'battered thatches' and 'thirsty souls who are hungry for love' (12). The massacre of the youths is so horrendous that even the physical environment joins in the mourning as can be seen in 'the soil and rivers mourn /heavy with the weight of the dead' (120). The survivors of the slain youths are made to bear the piercing pain of loss like a heartless bullet 'that rips apart their very existence' (12) while the dying screams of the fallen youths haunt them as 'sharp as the missiles that torment them day and night' (12). This way, their memory is fossilized (like

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tomorrow's debris) in the psyche of their survivors.

In the poem, 'Oloibiri', the poet projects her home town which incidentally is a name etched firmly in the annals of oil industry in Nigeria as the place where oil well was first drilled in 1958. However, the poet is saddened, because Oloibiri which is personified as an old woman has now been rejected and abandoned having yielded its wealth to the exploiters. The persona captures her pitiable situation thus 'now with my fertility gone: / I carry a begging bowl...' (14). The poet here shows the paradox of the Niger Delta which is the supplier of national wealth yet has to beg for survival. Oloibiri's later situation is compared to that of a whore whose stock in trade is the satisfaction of the lust of men while wasting away her youth. This is illustrated by the irony inherent in the lines:

Desolate like a wealthy aged whore...
Yet I quench the thirst of the desert dwellers.
Far and wide, my flow invents
Elegant monuments Gigantic
To the untutored sight of my people (13).

The poet in the above lines captures the oil politics of Nigeria which leaves the Delta reeling from the pain of deprivation and devastation while providing abundantly for distant arid places through the 'zebra strings of pipelines running through...' its belly causing it to 'ache from relentless exploitation'. A similar scenario is replicated in the poem '**Swamps of Our Time**'. Through the use of the rhetorical device, the poet arouses the consciousness of the people to the true situation of the Delta and in the process stirs in them the spirit of resistance. The persona asks: 'O delta of our beginning, /How has the past left you? / What is the future of your ecosystem?' (18). The persona reminisces on the openhearted and warm reception the Deltans accorded the exploiters who had come under the guise of developing the region: 'She welcomes from molar to molar/ traitors who danced to the rhythm of/ her broken heartbeats' (18). But the exploiters, having gained a foothold on the region, waste no time to bare their fangs on the people whom they wasted as 'sacrificial leeches' and sacrificial lambs meant to serve their greedy purpose. The exploiters thus see the people as expendable commodities to be discarded after serving their use by crushing them like one would leeches and parasites. It is this callous treatment of the indigenes like disposable waste that leaves a lasting, painful scar on the memory of the poet as seen in 'winds of bitter memory slap me silly/...deep scars of memory/ wrapped in cobwebs of pain' (19), and which feeds her determination for resistance.

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Conclusion

This paper has examined how lament, pain and protest constitute a common identity of Niger Delta poetry. The paper studied the poetry of four Niger Delta poets in order to ascertain the veracity of the above claim. Through a critical study of selected poems, the study found out that Niger Delta poetry is characterized by the temper and tenor of protest in order to create awareness about the need to resist the persisting onslaught against the Niger Delta environment by government and multinational oil companies so as to ensure environmental equity in the Niger Delta.

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